

Ego Strength Among Primary School Teachers of Muzaffarpur District, Bihar

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ABSTRACT

Ego strength is one of the major psychological aspects of human life. It's means strength of self. Ego strength is an individual's capacity to maintain his or her own identity despite psychological pain, distress, turmoil and conflict between internal forces as well as the demands of reality. This study investigates the level of ego strength among primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur district of Bihar using the Ego strength scale developed by Dr. Q. Hassan. The aim of this study was to study the impact of gender and residence on ego strength of primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur districts. A total 120 samples were selected from primary school of Muzaffarpur district by using random-cum-purposive sampling techniques. The collected data were analysed by using t-ratio with the help of SPSS software. This study shows that no any significant different between male and female primary school teachers and rural and urban primary school teachers, that means both gender groups and residential groups having similar levels of ego strength.

Keywords: Ego Strength and Primary School Teachers

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Introduction:

Ego strength means strength of self. It developed a capacity to adjust of an individual to perceive a challenging situation realistically and to execute the response effectively. Ego strength develops the capacity to adjustment in any challenging situation and motivates to play their actual role. According to Sigmund Freud (1930), 'The structure of personality the 'Ego' is the part of psychic structure and it is the mediator between 'Id' and 'Super ego'. Ego strength refers to the inner personal strength by which the men tolerate stress and frustration. It is the ego strength that allows us to infinitive defense mechanism. Ego strength is an important factor to determining the capacity of a teacher to perceive a challenging situation realistically and to execute the response effectively.

Symonds (1951) defines, 'Ego strength as the efficiency of the Ego in regulating impulses and mastering the environment. Ego strength is the capacity for sustaining emotional equilibrium while waiting or working for later gratification.'

According to Curtis (2017), 'Ego strength is a Psychological concept that refers to an individual's ability to cope with stress, deal with adversely and recover from setbacks when a person has good ego strength, they can manage the challenges that they face without resorting to harmful or unhealthy coping mechanisms.

This study investigates the ego strength among primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur district.

Review of literature:

Ego strength is a significant concern among primary school teacher. So, there are so many findings identified by the researchers on

Ego strength. Some important and researches and findings are discussed here.

Niloufar Farsijami, Mohammad Ali Beshart and Moghadamzadeh (2021) conducted a study on predicting social adjustment based on Ego strength and cognitive emotion regulation and the results showed that by increasing the individual score are adaptive strategies of emotion regulation and ego strength. The rate of social adjustment increases. Again it is suggested that to cultivate ego strength and teach cognitive emotion regulation strategies to promote social adjustment.

Swati Singh and Rajeev Singh (2017) studied the relationship between adjustment pattern and Ego strength among old age people of Patna at Ashiyana Nagar colony and found that high scores on Ego strength are effective and independent people can easily command over their own resources. They are intelligent, Social, Stable and somewhat original and they make their presence felt socially.

Barbara M. Gfellner & Ana I. Cordoba (2017) conducted a study on identity problems, Ego strength, perceived stress and adjustment during contextual changes at University and found that Ego strength moderated the relationship between perceived stress with academic and social adjustment respectively.

Naynika Singh & Anmol Anand (2015) conducted a study on the topic Ego strength and self concept among adolescents: A study on gender difference and found that there is no significant difference of ego strength among the female and male adolescents this shows that they are almost equally resilient in maintaining their emotions efficiency also males have been formed to be supportive and cooperative in assisting their female counterparts.

Mirshekari, Chanag and Zahed (2014) conducted an investigation to study the relationship between ego strength, self control and self esteem among 330 male and female students of University of Shahed and it was found that there is a correlation between all the

elements Ego strength was higher in women as compared to men and component of ego strength like care, love, loyalty, competence and hope were higher in women as compared to men.

V. Mishra (2013) conducted a study to analyze the self concept and ego strength of 80 visually impaired children and it was found that there is a positive relationship between ego strength and self concept again ego strength of the sighted students was higher than that of the visually impaired.

The above scenario clearly indicates that very few studies were carried out on this topic, so this study investigates the ego strength among primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur district of Bihar with the help of reliable tools.

Objective of the study:

In the above context, the present study proposed to examine the following research objectives:

- (i). To study the difference between ego strength of male and female primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur District.
- (ii). To study the difference between ego strength of rural and urban primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur District.

Hypotheses of the study:

The hypotheses of this study are given below:

- H₁.** There will be no significant difference in ego strength of male and female primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur District.
- H₂.** There will be no significant difference in ego strength of rural and urban primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur District.

Methodology:

This study uses the quantitative analysis of the data collected from primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur district of Bihar. A cross sectional study was carried out after taking consent of school administration and convenient sampling procedure was followed to select the participants was taken before the study.

A. Research Design:

The research design of this study was quantitative research design.

B. Sample:

In this study total 120 primary school teacher were selected from different primary school of Muzaffarpur district of Bihar by using random cum purposive sampling techniques. The sample is divided into two gender groups i.e., Male and Female and each group represented by 60 school teachers. The male and female has been further subdivided into two residential groups i.e., Rural and Urban and each group represented by 30 school teacher.

C. Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age between 18-60 years was included.
2. Minimum educational qualification of sample was graduate.

D. Exclusion Criteria:

1. Education qualification below graduation excluded.
2. Retired school teachers were excluded.

E. Tools:

The following tools were used in this research

1. Personal Data Sheet (PDS): This PDS was prepared by researchers himself for collecting the detailed information regarding participants including their name, age, gender, residence, qualification, name of college, name of father and address etc.

2. Ego strength scale (ESS):

Ego strength scale was used to measure the ego strength of the teacher. It has been developed by Dr. Q. Hasan, Department of Psychology, Aligarh muslim University and Published by Rupa Psychological Centre, Varanasi. This scale consists of 32 items. This scale has been administered on an individual as well as group both and take normally be completed 20 minutes. The reliability of this scale is 0.78 and the validity is 0.62.

E. Procedure:

Data were collected through self-administered questionnaires. After contacting the prospective participants and taking their consent, the Ego strength scale along with Personal data sheet were given to primary school teachers of Muzaffarpur district. The purpose of the study was explained and proper information was given to them. The primary school teacher gave their responses separately. After the screening the procedure was completed.

F. Ethics:

The participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity.

G. Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were analyzed by using statistics tools like- mean, standard deviation and t-test.

Result and discussion

The finding of the study has been tabulated in table- I and II respectively

Table – I

Comparison between male and female primary school teachers on ego strength scores

	N	M	SD	t	<P
Male teacher	60	18.89	8.46	.819	NS
Female teacher	60	19.94	5.37		

Table- I shows that ego strength of male and female primary school teachers. The N, M, SD score of male primary school teachers are 60, 18.89, 8.46 and the N, M, SD score of femae primary school teacher are 60, 19.94, 5.37 respectively. The t-score is .819, which not significant at any level.

Table – II

Comparison between rural and urban primary school teachers on ego strength scores

	N	M	SD	t	<P
Rural teacher	60	18.74	4.67	1.89	NS
Urban teacher	60	22.93	8.72		

Table- II shows that ego strength of rural and urban primary school teachers. The N, M, SD score of rural primary school teachers are 60, 18.74, 4.67 and the N, M, SD score of urban primary school teacher are 60, 22.93, 8.72 respectively. The t-score is 1.89, which not significant at any level.

Findings:

The findings of this study are as follows:

1. Both male and female primary school teachers having similar level of ego strength.
2. Both rural and urban primary school teachers having similar level of ego strength.

Conclusion:

The findings indicate that the ego strength is common among primary school teachers in Muzaffarpur district with no significant difference male and female primary school teachers and rural and urban primary school teachers at any levels. So, it's clear that ego strength is not affected by gender and residence.

Limitations and suggestion:

This study was conducted to the best of the researcher's quality and ability. The researchers take small size of sample, so extensive research should be conducted in future studies in this field and generalised the obtained results in large population. This study can be done by data collection from another district and state for universal acceptance.

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